
Policy Implementation and Service Efficiency Under Republic Act No. 11032: Assessing Awareness, Performance, and Implementation

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the implementation of Republic Act 11032 (Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act) in the 5th District of Iloilo, Philippines. A descriptive research design was employed, complemented by qualitative methods such as interviews and focus group discussions to capture the experiences of both local government unit (LGU) personnel and clients. Data was collected from 728 client respondents and 24 LGU representatives using a validated questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics and thematic analysis. Findings revealed that most clients have a moderate to high level of awareness of RA 11032 (weighted mean = 3.84), while LGUs reported a high level of implementation (weighted mean = 4.34). In terms of performance, LGUs were rated “very satisfactory” (weighted mean = 3.88), indicating that the law has contributed positively to improving service efficiency, transparency, and client satisfaction. Qualitative results further emphasized that RA 11032 promotes streamlined procedures, accountability, and trust between government offices and the public. However, several challenges persist, including limited manpower during peak hours, technical issues in digital systems, gaps in client awareness of procedures, and the need for continuous personnel training and better inter-office coordination. These issues affect the consistency of service delivery despite the overall positive implementation. The study concludes that while RA 11032 is effectively implemented in the province, continuous improvements in capacity building, system enhancement, and information dissemination are necessary. The findings highlight the importance of strengthening institutional support and adopting client-centered strategies to ensure sustainable, efficient and transparent public service delivery.

KEYWORDS: Republic Act 11032, Policy Implementation, Service Efficiency, Public Awareness, Government Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Good Governance depends on the efficiency and effectiveness of public services, which directly affect citizen satisfaction, economic activity, and overall development. Legislators, government leaders, and experts deliberately find ways for government offices to provide quality services to the Filipino people. The government enacted Republic Act No. 11032, also known as the Ease of Doing Business and Efficient Government Services Delivery Act of 2018, due to persistent bureaucratic inefficiencies. This landmark legislation mandates that government agencies, both national and local, streamline their processes, adopt strict service timelines, and implement systems to monitor good governance. This law aims to eradicate red tape and foster transparency, accountability, and citizen-centered governance. With this, citizens’ trust in our government services will improve.

Over the past few years, numerous studies have examined the implementation of RA11032, highlighting procedural reforms, technological services, and the adoption of feedback mechanisms. Just like, one study exposed that the implementation is too high but still needs more improvement. Like the clarity of the policy, we needed more study to ensure that clients' satisfaction reached its peak. These insights can help policymakers develop guidelines for effective performance (Temporal et al., 2025). Another study recommended an action plan to improve current policies and foster innovation. This action plan suggests improving communication, facilities, and employee skills to a state-of-the-art level (Quiatchon, 2024). However, these studies often focus on urban centers and national agencies, leaving limited empirical evidence on provincial local government units (LGUs), such as the 5th District of Iloilo, where resource constraints, administrative capacity, and local governance practices significantly influence policy implementation. Moreover, awareness campaigns and performance monitoring tools have been established, but discrepancies in understanding the laws, inconsistent application timelines, and variations in service efficiency persist across LGUs. These challenges showed that the mere presence of the policy mechanisms does not guarantee effective implementation or improve public service outcomes.

In Iloilo Province, composed of diverse municipalities and cities that operate under different administrative capacities, the context of awareness, adherence, and service efficiency under RA 11032 remains underexplored. Identifying these gaps is critical not only for assessing compliance but also for informing interventions that can enhance service delivery in local governance. By

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systematically assessing LGU awareness, performance, and policy implementation, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of RA 11032. Also, this is to know the operational at the provincial levels and to highlight actionable strategies for improvement. For instance, in the Municipality of Balasan, one research is on the services of the Municipal Civil Registry Office (MCRO) under the supervision of the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), which showed that the office is effectively implementing the services but is still looking for room for improvement (Billones, 2026).

Through this evaluation, the study contributes to the broader discourse on policy implementation. Government efficiency and service quality, offering evidence-based recommendations to support LGUs in fulfilling the objective of RA 11032. The findings are expected to guide policymakers, administrators, and scholars in enhancing public service delivery and ensuring that the law achieves its intended impact for citizens across the 5th District of Iloilo, and later the whole province.

1.1 Objective

Thus, this study aims to assess the implementation of Republic Act 11032, or the Ease of

Doing Business and Efficient Government Service Delivery Act of 2018, among LGUs in the 5th District of Iloilo by evaluating the level of awareness, level of performance, and level of implementation, and identifying factors that influence service efficiency and compliance.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study.

Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Research Study.

This study focuses on Republic Act 11032, signed by former President Rodrigo Roa Duterte on May 18, 2018, to improve the Anti-Red Tape Act of 2007. This new legislation seeks to mitigate the persistent problems of bureaucratic red tape, which often fosters inefficiency and corruption in the government. The main target of the law was to re-engineer the government systems, simplifying requirements and streamlining the procedures to reduce processing time and expedite transactions. As a summary, RA 11032 aims to promote transparency, accountability, and effectiveness in both business and non-business government transactions.

3. RELATED LITERATURE

The following themes are the focus of this review of related literature

3.1 Policy Implementation Theory and Governance Framework

Public Policy is a long-term procedure created by the government to address services, public demands, and design solutions to public problems. While governance is a rule-based system that includes cities, municipalities, and organizations, decisions are made; whether these decisions are executed or not is determined (Abas, 2022). Effective policy implementation remains one of the most continuing challenges in public policy and governance worldwide. Governments often develop a comprehensive, well-structured program framework that translates into workable government procedures. Yet outcomes remain problematic. A gap frequently emerges between policy intentions and actual practices, weakening service delivery, institutional performance, and public trust. For instance, in South Africa, the implementation deficit is particularly evident in complex socio-political and administrative systems. Structural inequalities, resource constraints, and governance capacity issues hinder the effective implementation of policy objectives (Jikwana et al., 2025). In Slovenia, the findings showed that problems such as a lack of evaluation practices and discontinuity at an early stage affect the implementation of the policy. This leads to poor inter-sectoral collaboration and insufficient, ineffective public discussions, resulting in poor policy implementation (Kotnik et al. 2020).

There is growing recognition that policies fail not because of their inherent merit; thus, policy design and implementation remain a persistent challenge for government agencies, not only in the Philippines but in all nations. But rather than draining from

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failures, the government continues to focus on strengthening the policy process from implementation, coordination, institutional support, and adaptive management to make it more sustainable.

In the Philippines, over the past decades, implementation gaps such as resource limitations, ambiguous guidelines, bureaucratic red tape, weak supervision, and misaligned budgets have led to inconsistencies in the government's policy execution. Leadership plays a significant role in the effective implementation of the policy. To address these issues, the findings suggest an integrated administrative framework. In addition, the report also recommends capacity building and agency coordination to promote more consistent, equitable, and responsive public service delivery (Fabaan et al., 2025). Also, one study highlights the essential importance of establishing clear, validated guidelines and structural frameworks to promote high-quality services across different government agencies that align with their own goals (Dalogdog & Cartin-Pecson, 2025).

3.2 Public Service Delivery and Government Efficiency

In the current technological landscape, digital transformation is key to improving efficiency, citizen engagement, and accountability in public services. By adopting digital transformation, improvements in organizational performance meet public expectations for higher-level mandates across government offices (Laturpeirissa et al., 2024). Although several LGUs have demonstrated notable success in service delivery, this confirms that local leadership capacity is more effective than the broader system. LGUs' officials are given sole authority; thus, they are independent in implementing policies that can help the economy grow (Velmonte, 2022). However, the success of implementing government services relies on infrastructure, resources, governance, stakeholder partnerships, and user-centered design. Just as E-governance operations do, these initiatives improve public service delivery by enhancing access, quality, and citizen engagement (Indama, 2023). When LGUs have visionary leaders, public service delivery and government efficiency become more accessible to the public. Satisfaction among constituents becomes highly positive.

3.3 Ease of Doing Business and Regulatory Reforms

The core principles of the Anti-Red Tape Act (ARTA) of 2007 are found in RA 11032, which includes the citizen charter, front-line services, and report card survey. A citizen charter outlines service standards and explains public expectations. While front-line services ensure that government services are readily accessible to all. The last one, the report card survey, is to evaluate service quality and serves as a feedback mechanism (Quiatchon, 2024). Furthermore, the new law establishes a standardized processing time; if it cannot be met, the agencies are required to write a letter to the client explaining the reason for the delay (Pestilos, 2019). In addition, the law required LGUs and other agencies to establish a Business One-Stop Shop (BOSS) and an online platform to streamline transactions. Permits and licenses are processed through BOSS. However, there are some LGUs where the process for barangay clearance, business permits, mayor's permit, and location and zoning clearance is digitized or not (Mendoza, 2025).

Additionally, the law streamlines business processes, making them faster, simpler, and more transparent. The forms are unified, and preliminary evaluations to correct deficiencies are applied. This results in fewer transactions and all clearances issued together in the BOSS. Deadlines are set for simple tasks (3 days), complex tasks (around 7 days), and highly technical tasks (20 days). There is also an automated approval system to ensure deadlines are not missed. Government agencies have specific functions, such as the Department of Information and Communication Technology (DICT), which is responsible for the online central business portal. One unique feature is the eradication of corruption in the government. LGUs and NGAs established a citizen charter detailing the steps of government transactions (Brima, 2019).

3.4 Philippines Public Administration and Local Governance

To improve LGU services across the entire archipelago, the Local Government Code, or RA 7160, was enacted in 1991 to allow the four-tier structure (provinces, cities, municipalities, barangays) in the Philippines greater autonomy, thereby easing government operations and enhancing transparency. But this centralization faces various challenges, including political patronage, limited revenue generation, and weak local capacity. These issues and problems persist after 30 years of the law's implementation (Atienza & Go, 2023). This is also experienced in Northern Iloilo, Philippines, where problems affect the effective and efficient performance of local governance. Each of the municipalities within the district have their own specific strategies that sometimes cause conflicts of interest among

3.5 Digital Governance and E-Government Efficiency

One of the most innovative strategies LGUs have adopted in recent years is the digital transformation to make overall government transactions efficient. One study exposed the novel theoretical framework of digital governance that offers suggestions for optimizing allocation and strategies to advance public sector performance (Yang et al., 2024). Thus, one study recommends allocating a budget for the yearly procurement of ICT for long-term investment to respond to the call for good governance (Manlapas & Mantillas, 2024). Also, computer literacy and data use among LGUs in the Province of Antique are endorsed in one study. The results suggest that LGUs that used ICT for all transactions were their own best practices (Yumen, 2023).

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4. METHODS

4.1 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to examine the effectiveness of RA1103's implementation in the 5th District of Iloilo, Philippines. However, to make the results relevant and scholarly, the researcher also integrated a qualitative design, specifically individual interviews and focus-group discussions (FGD), to deepen understanding of respondents' experiences with the operation of the law in each municipality in Northern Iloilo.

4.2 Study Locale and Sampling Procedure

This study was conducted in the 5th District of the Province of Iloilo, composed of eleven municipalities ranging from 1st to 4th class. With a total population of 472,661. The sampling technique used a cluster design to select LGUs within the 5th district to ensure proportional representation across municipalities, while purposive sampling was employed to identify the specific respondents among employees of selected LGUs. The respondents were both BPLO employees and clients with direct experience in business permit transactions.

4.3 Data Collection

A self-structured questionnaire was developed to gather information on the level of implementation of RA 11032. This questionnaire was validated and pilot-tested to ensure strong results on the topics before the full deployment.

4.4 Data Analysis

The collected data were systematically organized and categorized. Descriptive statistics, such as means, frequencies, and percentages, were used to summarize respondents' responses. Also, the qualitative part was coded, themed, and triangulated.

4.5 Ethical Consideration

This study adhered to establish ethical standards to ensure the protection, privacy, and well-being of all the participants. Participation in this research study is purely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained prior to the study. Each of them was informed about the study and its purpose. Pseudonyms or codes were used to maintain respondents' confidentiality. The responses were securely stored on the researcher's personal computer, protected by a password and used solely for academic purposes.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1 shows the Level of Awareness in the implementation of RA 11032.

Table 1. Distribution of client-respondents according to their level of awareness in the implementation of RA 11032

LEVEL OF AWARENESS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF RA 11032	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
<i>Slightly Aware</i>	15	2.1
<i>Moderately Aware</i>	131	18.0
<i>Aware</i>	375	51.5
<i>Fully Aware</i>	207	28.4
<i>Total</i>	728	100.0

Weighted Mean: 3.84 à Aware

The distribution of client-respondents' awareness of RA 11032 indicates that a majority have a moderate to high understanding of the law. Specifically, 375 respondents (51.5%) were aware, 207 (28.4) were fully aware, 131 (18%) were moderately aware, and only 15 respondents (2.1%) were slightly aware. The overall weighted mean of 3.84, interpreted as "Aware," suggests that clients are generally knowledgeable about the provisions of RA 11032. While most clients understand the objectives of the law, some may still have difficulty fully comprehending all specific provisions, indicating a need for continued information dissemination and client education to enhance understanding.

The findings indicate that most client-respondents have a moderate to high level of awareness of RA 11032, with more than half being generally aware and nearly a third being fully aware of the law. This suggests that the law's objectives, such as streamlining government transactions, reducing bureaucratic red tape, and promoting transparency, have been effectively communicated to the public. However, the presence of a small proportion of respondents who are only slightly aware highlights a gap in outreach and public education.

From a governance perspective, awareness is a critical factor in ensuring that citizens can fully utilize and benefit from government services. Clients who are knowledgeable about RA 11032 are more likely to engage confidently with LGU processes, comply with requirements efficiently, and hold government offices accountable for the timely delivery of services. On the other hand, limited understanding among some clients may result in missed opportunities, miscommunication, or dissatisfaction with services, thereby undermining the law's intended impact.

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These findings underscore the need for sustained, targeted information campaigns, such as public seminars, digital information drives, and clear, accessible guides on RA 11032 procedures. By enhancing citizens' understanding of their rights and the expected service standards, LGUs can improve service efficiency, increase compliance, and foster greater trust and cooperation between the government and the public.

While the high level of awareness among most clients reflects positive strides in law dissemination, addressing the remaining knowledge gaps is essential to maximize the benefits of RA 11032 and ensure equitable access to efficient government services.

Table 2. Distribution of LGU-respondents according to their level of implementation in the Province of Iloilo of RA 11032

LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF RA 11032 AMONG LGUs IN THE PROVINCE OF ILOILO	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Implemented	11	45.8
Fully Implemented	13	54.2
Total	24	100.0

Weighted Mean: 4.34 à Fully Implemented

Among the LGU respondents in the Province of Iloilo, 13 LGUs (54.3%) reported that RA 11032 was fully implemented, while 11 LGUs (45.8%) reported that it was implemented to a fair extent. The weighted mean score of 4.34, interpreted as "Fully Implemented," reflects that LGUs recognize RA 11032 as a mandatory framework and have largely integrated its requirements into their operations. This finding demonstrates a strong commitment among LGUs to comply with the law and streamline government service delivery, supporting its objective of promoting efficiency and transparency in local governance.

The high level of reported implementation aligns with previous studies emphasizing that organizational commitment and adherence to formal policies are critical for effective public service delivery (Lo et al., 2024). By fully operationalizing RA 11032, LGUs are likely to improve procedural efficiency, ensure standardized processing times, and minimize direct contact between citizens and front-line staff, thereby reducing opportunities for delays and corruption (Temporal et al., 2025). However, the near-equal proportion of LGUs reporting partial implementation highlights that resource limitations, capacity gaps, and procedural challenges may still hinder uniform compliance across all municipalities (Magno-Ballesteros et al., 2023).

These findings indicate that while RA 11032 has been widely embraced as a guiding framework, continuous support, monitoring, and capacity-building initiatives are essential to sustain full implementation and achieve consistent, transparent, and efficient service delivery across all LGUs in the Province of Iloilo.

Table 3 presents the level of performance in implementing RA 11032 in the municipalities of Northern Iloilo.

Table 3. Distribution of client-respondents who rated the performance of LGUs in the implementation of RA 11032

LEVEL OF PERFORMANCE OF LGUs IN THE PROVINCE OF ILOILO OF RA 11032	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Needs Improvement	3	.4
Fair	26	3.6
Satisfactory	210	28.8
Very Satisfactory	304	41.8
Outstanding	185	25.4
Total	728	100.0

Weighted Mean: 3.88 à Very Satisfactory

Client evaluations of LGU performance in implementing RA 11032 further support these findings. A significant proportion of respondents rated LGUs as very satisfactory (304 respondents, 41.8%), while 210 respondents (28.8%) rated them as satisfactory, and 185 respondents (25.4%) rated performance as outstanding. Only a small minority of LGUs received lower ratings; 26 respondents (3.6%) rated performance as fair, and 3 respondents (0.4%) rated performance as needing improvement. The weighted mean score of 3.88, interpreted as "Very Satisfactory," suggests that, from the clients' perspectives, LGUs are performing well in implementing RA 11032. This aligns with the high level of reported implementation and indicates that the law is positively influencing service delivery outcomes.

These results align with the reported high level of implementation and demonstrate that LGUs are largely successful in operationalizing the law's provisions, including standardized processing times, the Zero-Contact Policy, and streamlined procedures for business permits and licensing. This finding is consistent with prior studies indicating that proper policy implementation positively influences service delivery outcomes and citizen satisfaction (Tempora et al., 2025; Gonzales & De Castro, 2024). When

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citizens perceive services as efficient, transparent, and accessible, their trust in government institutions tends to increase, thereby reinforcing compliance and strengthening governance (Alessandro et al., 2021).

However, the presence of a minority rating LGU performance as fair or needing improvement highlights that those challenges remain, potentially stemming from uneven resource allocation, capacity constraints, or procedural bottlenecks. These disparities underscore the need for continuous monitoring, targeted capacity-building initiatives, and constitutional support to ensure consistent service quality across all LGUs. Overall, the findings suggest that RA 11032 is not only being implemented but also effectively enhancing public satisfaction and promoting higher standards of local governance in Iloilo Province.

Despite generally positive results, several challenges were identified. From the clients' perspective, the inadequacy of frontline service providers in attending to client needs was the primary issue, followed by undefined procedures for processing permits/licenses, and unorganized Business Permit and Licensing Offices (BPOs). From the LGUs' perspective, the inadequacy of supplies, equipment, and facilities was the main obstacle, with insufficient front-line personnel and lack of training for service providers ranking second and third, respectively. These findings highlight the need for capacity-building initiatives, improved resource allocation, and procedural standardization to overcome implementation bottlenecks and enhance service efficiency.

The results indicate a positive relationship between awareness, implementation, and performance in the context of RA 11032. Clients who are aware of the law tend to experience better service delivery, while LGUs that fully implement the law achieve higher performance ratings. However, gaps in front-line capacity, resources, and standardized procedures suggest that continued support and targeted interventions are necessary to fully realize the law's objectives. Strengthening training programs, upgrading facilities, and clarifying procedural workflows could further improve LGUs' efficiency, transparency, and responsiveness in Iloilo Province. Table 4 shows the responses to the Awareness of RA 11032

Table 4. Responses to the Question “How do you Understand RA 11032 and its Importance in your Office?”

Themes	Responses
Awareness of RA 11032	<p>RA 11032 helps ensure faster and more transparent transactions, which benefits both employees and clients</p> <p>It is an important law that reduces red tape and promotes accountability in public service</p> <p>I understand it as a guideline to make the service more efficient and client-friendly.</p> <p>It reminds us to follow standard processing times and avoid unnecessary delays.</p> <p>The law improves trust between the institution and the public</p>

The qualitative responses regarding awareness of RA 11032 reveal a strong, consistent understanding among participants of the law's purpose and its significance for public services. The analysis of responses yielded several key themes: efficiency, transparency, accountability, standardization, and public trust. Respondents commonly described RA 11032 as a mechanism that enables faster, more transparent transactions, highlighting its direct benefits to both employees and clients. This reflects an appreciation of the law's role in streamlining processes and minimizing service delivery delays. The emphasis on transparency also indicates that participants recognize the importance of openness in fostering a more responsive and client-centered environment. Another dominant theme is the reduction of red tape and the promotion of accountability. Participants acknowledged that the law serves as a safeguard against unnecessary bureaucratic procedures, reinforcing responsible and ethical practices among personnel. This aligns with the core objectives of RA 11032, which is to institutionalize efficiency and integrity in government services.

The findings showed no significant relationship between basic facilities and the selected policy areas, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The study recommends improving communication, upgrading facilities, and accountability (Quiatchon, 2024). The study concludes that implementation is strong but can be improved by enhancing service accessibility, feedback, and, procedural clarity to better satisfy clients (Temporal et al., 2025).

As a result, the university actively follows the government's policy directives, particularly in improving and streamlining systems and processes. This is managed through the university's Quality Management Unit under the University President's Office, and the university consistently implements the zero-contact policy to ensure ease of doing business, in line with national mandates (Tolentino, 2024).

Moreover, the respondent viewed the laws as a guideline for improving service efficiency and client-friendliness, suggesting that they are not only understood but also applied in daily operations. The mention of adherence to standard processing times further indicated that participants are aware of the law's specific provisions and their practical implications. Importantly, the theme of trust-building emerged from the responses, with participants noting that RA 11032 strengthens the relationship between the institution and the public. Institution. In general, the findings suggest that respondents have a high level of awareness of RA 11032, with a clear understanding of its goals and benefits. This level of awareness is essential, as it serves as a foundation for effective implementation and improved service efficiency.

The importance of openness in fostering a more responsive and client-centered environment.

Table 5 presents responses to the theme of experiences during policy implementation.

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Table 5. Responses of the Respondents on the Question, “How is RA 11032 Implemented in your Office?”

Themes	Responses
Experience in Policy Implementation	Our office has posted clear procedures and processing times for all the transactions. We follow a first-come, first-served policy and ensure that the clients are accommodated promptly. There are designated personnel to assist clients and answer inquiries. Feedback mechanisms such as suggestion boxes and online forms are available. Although implementation is generally good, delays can occur due to system issues.

The findings indicate that the office demonstrates a strong and structured approach to policy implementation. Clear procedures and posted processing times provide transparency and help clients understand the steps involved in transactions, while the first-come, first-served policy ensures fairness and prompt attention. Designation personnel are available to assist clients and address inquiries, reflecting the office’s commitment to accessibility and responsive service. Additionally, feedback mechanisms, such as suggestion boxes and online forms, show that client input is valued and used to improve service processes.

The findings show that the office provides efficient and well-organized services, with most transactions completed promptly and waiting times reduced over the years. The implementation of digital systems had helped streamline processes and improve overall speed. However, during busy period, service efficiency can be affected, highlighting the need for better resource management, staff allocation, and process improvements to maintain smooth, consistent service for all clients (Criveanu, 2026). The study found that SMEs in Albay are adopting e-commerce despite facing challenges. Key factors positively influence this integration, and the study provides practical strategies for policymakers to support and enhance e-commerce implementation for these enterprises (Flores, 2025).

However, despite these effective practices, occasional delays due to system issues were reported, underscoring the need to address technical challenges to maintain consistent efficiency. Overall, the office exhibits a high level of compliance with policy guidelines, and with improvements in system reliability, it can further enhance service delivery, client satisfaction, and overall policy effectiveness.

Table 6 exposes the responses on the theme of service efficiency.

Table 6. Responses of the Respondents on the Question, “How would you describe the efficiency of Service in your Office?”

Themes	Responses
Service Efficiency	Services are generally fast and organized, especially on regular days. Most transactions are completed within the prescribed time. There is improvement compared to previous years, particularly in reducing waiting time. Efficiency is evident, but it becomes challenging during peak periods. Digital systems have helped speed up processes.

The office demonstrates a high level of service efficiency, with transactions generally processed quickly and in an organized manner, and waiting times noticeably reduced compared to previous years. The use of digital systems has further streamlined processes, improving accuracy and speed. However, efficiency can be affected during peak periods, underscoring the need for better resource allocation, scheduling, and process optimization to consistently and reliably deliver service.

The study’s findings are based on data collected from DMS users via a questionnaire. The results indicate that an organization’s level of maturity significantly influences the life cycle of its Document Management System (DMS). Organizations that effectively manage the DMS life cycle are better equipped to handle digital transformation and address sustainability challenges associated with the transition to a paperless environment (Zabukovšel et al., 2023).

Table 7 presents the responses to the theme of personnel performance.

Table 7. The responses on the question “How do personnel contribute to service efficiency.”

Themes	Responses
Performance of Personnel	Staff are approachable and willing to assist clients with their concerns. Personnel are knowledgeable about procedures and policies. They handle clients professionally and respectfully. Employee teamwork helps speed up transactions. Some staff need additional training to further improve service delivery.

The personnel generally perform well, demonstrating professionalism, knowledge of procedures, and a willingness to assist clients. Teamwork among staff contributes to faster, smoother transactions, thereby enhancing overall service efficiency. However, the study suggests that providing additional training for some employees could further strengthen service delivery and ensure consistently high-quality client interactions.

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Continuous learning and growth help employees develop the skills needed for innovation. Structured, field-specific learning programs improve technical abilities, soft skills, and work ethic, ultimately enhancing organizational performance and enabling employees to handle non-routine tasks creatively (Sadewa & Ridwan, 2024).

Table 8 shows the responses of the respondents to the thematic challenges encountered

Table 8. The responses to the question, “What Challenges do you encounter in implementing RA 11032?”

Themes	Responses
Challenges Encountered	Limited manpower slows service during peak hours. Technical issues with online systems sometimes cause delays. Some clients are not aware of the procedures that slow down transactions. There is a need for continuous personnel training. Coordination between offices can still be improved.

The study revealed several challenges that impact service delivery. Limited manpower during peak hours slowed transactions, highlighting the need for adequate staffing to manage high client volumes effectively. Technical issues with online systems also contributed to delays, indicating the importance of regular system maintenance and support. Additionally, some clients were unfamiliar with procedures, further slowing transactions and underscoring the need for clear guidance and communication. Continuous training for personnel was identified as essential to strengthen their skills and improve service performance. Coordination between offices also requires improvement, as better communication and collaboration could significantly enhance overall efficiency and client satisfaction.

The study revealed a need for expertise in computerization, digital innovation, and technological advancement, highlighting that the city has yet to fully adapt to the Ease of Doing Business (EODB) framework. Streamlined procedures, a key component of the law, are not consistently practiced in the city. To address these gaps, the study proposes an Action Plan to the systems and procedures at the Business One Stop Shop, implementing an electronic database, updating the City’s Citizens’ Charter, providing alternative payment options, bench-marking practices with other local government units in Laguna (Biglete, 2023).

Table 9 presents the responses to the them suggestions for improvement.

Table 9. The Responses to the Question, “What Suggestions can you give to Improve the Implementation and Service Efficiency?”

Themes	Responses
Suggestions for Improvement	Provide regular training and seminars for employees Improve the digital system to minimize delays. Increase manpower during peak periods. Enhance information dissemination to clients. Strengthen monitoring and evaluation of service delivery.

The study highlighted several recommendations to enhance service delivery and operational efficiency. Providing regular training and seminars for employees was emphasized to ensure that staff remain well-equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to handle client concerns effectively. Upgrading and improving the digital system was also suggested to reduce delays and streamline processes, thereby ensuring smoother, faster transactions.

Increasing the manpower during peak periods was identified as an important measure to manage high client volumes and minimize waiting times. Additionally, improving the dissemination of information to clients can help them better understand procedures, reducing confusion and unnecessary delays. Finally, strengthening service delivery monitoring and evaluation was recommended to ensure consistent quality, identify areas for improvement, and support ongoing organizational development. Together, these measures aim to create a more efficient, responsive, and client-centered service environment.

6. CONCLUSION

The study’s findings indicate that the implementation of Republic Act 11032 in the Province of Iloilo is generally effective, as evidenced by high client awareness, strong compliance among LGUs, and very satisfactory performance ratings, most respondents demonstrate a clear understanding of the law’s purpose, particularly in promoting efficiency, transparency, and accountability in public service. Likewise, LGUs have largely institutionalized their provisions, resulting in improved service delivery, streamlined procedures, and increased client satisfaction.

However, despite these positive outcomes, several challenges remain. Issues such as limited manpower during peak hours, technical difficulties in digital systems, gaps in client awareness of procedures, and the need for continuous personnel training and better inter-office coordination affect the consistency of service delivery. These concerns highlight that while implementation is strong, it

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is not yet uniform across all areas. The study further emphasizes that awareness, implementation, and performance are interconnected. Higher client awareness contributes to smoother transactions, while effective implementation by LGUs leads to better performance outcomes. To sustain and further enhance these gains, continuous improvements are necessary, particularly in capacity building, system upgrades, and information dissemination. Overall, RA 11032 has significantly improved governance and public service efficiency in Iloilo. Strengthening existing practices and addressing identified gaps will help ensure more consistent, inclusive, and client-centered service delivery, ultimately maximizing the benefits of the law for both government institutions and the public.

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